

Improved Power Conversion Efficiency of P3HT:PCBM Organic Solar Cells by Strong Spin–Orbit Coupling-Induced Delayed Fluorescence

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Solution-processed organic bulk heterojunction solar cells based on poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT) blended with [6,6]-phenyl-C₆₀-butyric acid methyl ester are doped with different concentrations of iron (II,III) oxide nanoparticles (Fe₃O₄). The power conversion efficiency of the devices doped at low concentrations is improved up to 11%. The improvement finds its origin in a lower recombination current, which is a consequence of an increased effective exciton lifetime according to the *J*-*V* characteristics and the optoelectronic analysis of the films. The increase in performance cannot be attributed to changes in morphology or crystallinity according to grazing-incidence X-ray scattering experiments. The evolution of the solar cell short-circuit current at low doping concentrations is related to variations in the arrangement of the crystalline regions of P3HT. For high doping concentrations (above 1.0 wt%) the performance of the solar cell decays rapidly, ascribed to the increased leakage currents in the device caused by the presence of nanoparticles.

1. Introduction

Over the past years organic photovoltaics have been the focus of an increasing interest due to their flexible, semitransparent, and light-weight properties, as well as due to their suitability for implementation with both lab-environment deposition techniques, such as spin coating, as well as potential for further low-cost manufacturing processes like spray coating or slot die coating.^[1–7] Moreover, rapid energy payback times are envisaged for organic solar cells (OSCs).^[8] OSCs have so far reached top power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) over 10% and, amongst the different possible combinations of donor–acceptor materials used for production of the active layer, poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT) and [6,6]-phenyl-C₆₀-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM)

commercial availability of the two components.^[9,10] So far, the greatest boost for enhancement of device efficiencies has been yielded through the introduction of the bulk heterojunction (BHJ) configuration, in which donor and acceptor materials are mixed in solution yielding a nanoscale-mixed blend as active layer.^[11,12] A close intermixing between donor and acceptor materials is of capital importance in order to ensure a high rate of photogenerated excitons dissociated into charge carriers, since the limited diffusion length of singlet excitons (reported in the range of 3–6 nm for P3HT) sets the spatial scale in which exciton splitting occurs efficiently.^[13,14] These facts have pushed many groups to improve the donor–acceptor morphology arrangement

via nanostructuring, by selecting different solvents or by adding solvent additives for morphology control for blend processing, such as, e.g., diiodooctane or octanedithiol.^[15–23]

Given the difficulty to tune the morphology between donor and acceptor materials at such small scales, another way around this issue that has gained attention consists of increasing the effective lifetime of the photogenerated excitons, and thereby their diffusion length.^[24,25] Whilst the singlet excitons in P3HT have a reported lifetime of approximately 300 ps, corresponding to a diffusion length of 3–6 nm, the triplet excitons present a lifetime of the order of 10 μs, yielding an effective diffusion length of about 100 nm.^[26] The reason for this is that the ground state of most of the organic molecules is electrically neutral and with spin zero, i.e., a singlet ground state. Therefore, the spin quantum selection rule prevents the excited triplet excitons to decay radiatively to the ground state, which causes phosphorescence to be a low-efficiency decay mechanism in organic molecules. Moreover, because of the same reason, triplet excitons cannot be excited by the absorption of light, since photons do not present coupling to electron spins, owing to the fact that electromagnetic radiation does not carry any torque.^[27] Therefore, the migration of excitonic states from the excited singlet to the triplet manifolds leads to an increased effective diffusion length of the photogenerated excitons. This transition is known as “intersystem crossing” or “spin rephasing”, and according to the quantum selection rules it is forbidden,

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account for the most widely studied pair due to easy

since it implies a spin flip.^[28–30] However, relaxation of the spin selection rule can occur in the presence of a strong spin–orbit coupling, in which the quantum state of the system $n_{\rightarrow}e_{\rightarrow}d_{\rightarrow}s_{\rightarrow}$ to \rightarrow be described by the total quantum angular momentum $J = L + S$ of the system. This gives rise to weak spin-forbidden bands, with an overlap between the singlet and triplet states. The phosphorescence efficiency can be enhanced by the presence of heavy atoms, either in the main polymer chain or blended with the active layer, typically in the form of heavy metal nanoparticles (NPs).^[28,32] Other phenomena appointed as responsible for singlet–triplet transitions are, for instance, the Zeeman or the hyperfine interactions.^[31,32,29,30,33]

Besides the above-mentioned advantages, the inclusion of small heavy metal NPs in the active layer can have an effect on the film morphology, the donor–acceptor intermixing scales, and the degree of crystallinity as well as crystal orientation, which in the end has an impact on the conductivity and therefore on the performance of the final device. Thus, a complex interplay between these factors will make the prediction of a potential positive effect of the efficiency of OSCs very difficult. Moreover, a very large number of different small heavy metal NPs are available and could be added to OSCs. For a reasonable selection, the NPs should be compatible with organic solvents, be non-toxic, and readily available in the desired volume/surface ratio.

In order to discuss in which way the performance of OSCs doped with metal oxide NPs is mainly affected, we present a study based on the model system P3HT:PCBM solar cells blended with different weight concentrations of iron (II,III) oxide (Fe_3O_4) NPs. The obtained current density–voltage J – V characteristics for the solar cells doped with different concentrations of Fe_3O_4 NPs are closely studied with the aid of spectral (fluorescence and phosphorescence) and morphological characterization (grazing-incidence small/wide-angle X-ray scattering).

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Solar Cell Performance

The PCE of P3HT:PCBM solar cells doped with various concentrations of Fe_3O_4 NPs under AM 1.5G illumination (1000 W m^{-2}) is displayed in **Figure 1a**.

An increase in PCE with respect to the reference solar cell (i.e., the one with 0 wt% of Fe_3O_4 NPs) is found at low doping concentrations. Such an increase was already reported in a previous investigation on the same system.^[34] The NP concentration dependence of the PCE is closely linked to that of the fill factor (FF), as can be seen in **Figure 1**. The maximum improvement in PCE as well as in FF is found at 0.6 wt% NPs, yielding 11% improvement in efficiency with respect to the reference solar cell (from 3.05% to 3.37%) and 12% improvement in FF (from 56.5% to 63.5%). However, all the solar cells up to this NP concentration threshold lead to a higher PCE than that of the reference cell, whereas the FF shows an improvement up to 0.8 wt% NPs. **Figure 2** displays the evolution of J_{sc} and V_{oc} plotted against the concentration of Fe_3O_4 NPs. J_{sc} presents a slight decrease for 0–0.8 wt% Fe_3O_4 NPs. This decrease is

Figure 1. a) PCE η and b) fill factor measured for P3HT:PCBM solar cells containing different weight percentages of Fe_3O_4 NPs concentration. Dashed lines are guide to the eye.

appointed as the reason why the solar cells with 0.8 wt% NPs perform worse than the reference (0 wt%), although the FF shows an improvement. Beyond this threshold, J_{sc} decreases rapidly.

A similar behavior is found in the V_{oc} , which shows a slight increase up to 1.05 wt% NPs and a strong decrease at higher NP concentrations. The latter fact displays an enhanced leakage current in the device, which also fits the rapid decay of the shunt resistance R_{SH} beyond Fe_3O_4 NP concentrations of 1.05% (not shown). This owes to the increased presence of Fe_3O_4 NPs in the active layer. Fe_3O_4 is an electrical conductor with conductivity values about six orders of magnitude higher than regular hematite (Fe_2O_3), which is attributed to electron exchange between Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} centers.^[35] Thus, a higher concentration of Fe_3O_4 NPs enables alternative conducting paths for the charge carriers, thereby inducing strong leakage currents and thus decreasing R_{SH} , J_{sc} , and V_{oc} . Arising of conductive pathways by the presence of Fe_3O_4 is not hindered by the oleic acid (OA) capping, since the interaction of the latter with the organic solvent prevents it from forming a compact layer around the NP (<1.0% OA; see Experimental Section). A strong increase in conductivity provided by OA-capped Fe_3O_4 NPs in

Figure 2. a) Short-circuit current J_{sc} and b) open circuit voltage V_{oc} measured for P3HT:PCBM solar cells containing different weight percentages of Fe₃O₄ NPs. Dashed lines are guide to the eye.

poly(thiophene)-based matrices was for example previously reported by Kim et al.^[36]

Figure 3 shows the evolution of series (R_s) and shunt (R_{SH}) resistances for the solar cells with 0–1.05 wt% Fe₃O₄ NPs. It can be seen how the variations in R_s and R_{SH} are minimal in the range of solar cell improvement, i.e., up to 0.8 wt% NPs. Provided that the improvement in FF takes place without major variations in R_s and R_{SH} , it is concluded that the increase in the FF has its origin in the diode region. This means that the solar cell performance in the Fe₃O₄ NP concentration of interest is more dominated by the diffusion current, i.e., less dominated by recombination current. Thereby the ideality factor of the device is shifted towards 1, being the ideality factor for a device governed by diffusion current, whereas a device dominated by recombination current would present an ideality factor of 2.^[37]

2.2. Morphology Characterization (GISAXS)

From the study of the solar cell J - V characteristics, a reduction of the recombination current in P3HT:PCBM OSCs for low concentrations of Fe₃O₄ NPs is noticed. This improvement

Figure 3. Series resistance R_s (solid circles) and shunt resistances R_{SH} (hollow circles) of P3HT:PCBM solar cells with different weight percentages of Fe₃O₄ NPs. Dashed lines are guide to the eye.

is ascribed to the increased rate of intersystem crossing for the excitons in the system, owing to the strong spin-orbit coupling induced by the presence of Fe₃O₄ NPs in the active layer. However, it is known that incorporation of embedded bodies in donor-acceptor blends, such as NPs, influences their demixing behavior and arrangement scale.^[38,39] Therefore, in order to check if the improvement observed in the solar cells does find its origin in any morphological change, grazing-incidence small-angle X-ray scattering (GISAXS) measurements are performed on P3HT:PCBM samples doped with the corresponding different concentrations of Fe₃O₄ NPs. The GISAXS technique is very well suited for thin film characterization.^[40–42] It allows for tracking of domain sizes and arrangement with a resolution ranging from few to hundreds of nanometers.^[43,44] The probed sample area is of the order of the pixel size of the OSCs, which allows for a direct comparison between structure and function.^[45] The 2D GISAXS patterns recorded for different NP concentrations and a detailed description about features in these GISAXS data can be found in Figure S1 (Supporting Information).

For analysis, horizontal line cuts of the 2D GISAXS data are performed at the Yoneda peak position. This peak is material characteristic and it is observed at the critical angle of the material.^[46] Horizontal line cuts are performed at a fixed q_z value and they yield structure information parallel to the sample surface, thereby allowing for a characterization of lateral structures such as domain sizes and center-to-center distances within the active layer. These horizontal line cuts are displayed in **Figure 4a** with increasing concentration of Fe₃O₄ NPs from bottom to top. The curves are fitted with a model consisting of four form factors with cylindrical geometry distributed over a 1D paracrystal lattice. As a result of these fits for each sample, characteristic structure information is obtained, which describes the morphology. We get four average domain sizes as well as four center-to-center distances. The evolution of both types of features, domain sizes and center-to-center distances, is displayed in Figure 4b,c for different concentrations of Fe₃O₄ NPs, respectively. The error bars associated with each point are obtained from the fitting tolerance. Fits with a lower number of scattering objects were not successful.

Figure 4. a) Horizontal line cuts obtained from the 2D GISAXS data for samples with different Fe_3O_4 NP concentrations (0, 0.1, 0.6, 0.8, 1.05, 2.0, 3.0, and 4.0 wt% from bottom to top). Gray lines indicate the fits to the data. Cuts are shifted along the intensity axis for illustrative purposes. Average b) domain size and c) interdomain distance for different Fe_3O_4 doping levels. The values are extracted from the fits.

Amongst the four form and structure factors identified in the fitting, three of them correspond to P3HT:PCBM domains. The fourth corresponds to the peak visible at high q -values, which increases in intensity along with the concentration of Fe_3O_4 NPs. The origin of these maxima at high q -values is concluded to come from the presence of the Fe_3O_4 NPs (see Supporting Information). The extracted value of the NP radius obtained from the fits (4.9 ± 0.3 nm) is in good agreement with the nominal values provided by the NP supplier (radii 4.5–5.5 nm).

In terms of domain sizes and the center-to-center distances associated with the domains in the P3HT:PCBM blend (Figure 4b,c), three different families need to be discussed. For the big domains, a slight decrease in radii is found (from 120 ± 20 nm for the sample with 0.0 wt% to 80 ± 8 nm for the one with 4.0 wt% NPs). Similarly, the structure factor associated with this domain family decreases from 240 ± 40 nm (0.0 wt% NPs) to 160 ± 30 nm (4.0 wt% NPs). These variations in size and interdomain distance occur almost within the deviation associated with the corresponding mean values. Moreover, due to the large sizes and big distances for the whole range of Fe_3O_4 NP concentrations, the change in morphology of these domains is not expected to play an important role in the recombination current of the solar cell, since the typical sizes associated are far away from the reach of the singlet excitons. The medium- sized and small families present as well only slight variations in radii and center-to-center distance upon the addition of NPs. The medium-sized family varies over the whole range of concentrations only from 48 ± 4 nm (0.0 wt% NPs) to 35 ± 4 nm (4.0 wt% NPs) in domain radius and from 90 ± 20 nm (0.0 wt% NPs) to 60 ± 15 nm (4.0 wt% NPs) in center-to-center distance. The latter changes in structure factors occur, then, completely within overlap of the respective deviations and, thus, can be considered that the change is practically negligible. Finally, the family depicting the smallest domains, corresponding to the P3HT:PCBM closest intermixing, remains basically unchanged in radius (from 5.0 ± 0.8 nm for the sample with 0.0 wt% to 6.0 ± 1.0 nm for the one with 4.0 wt% NPs) and in center-to-center distance (10 ± 0.5 nm at 0.0 wt% to 10 ± 1.0 nm at 4.0 wt% NPs). Morphological features in P3HT:PCBM films on such a scale relevant for exciton dissociation were observed and reported previously.^[47]

Generally, we conclude that although slight changes in typical sizes of the domains inside the active layers occur upon addition of Fe_3O_4 NPs, these appear to be way too gentle for being appointed as responsible for the improvement in the PCE of the solar devices. Moreover, the variations observed in GISAXS do not correlate with the range of NP concentrations for which the PCE values exhibit an increase.

2.3. Spectral Response (Photoluminescence)

From the GISAXS measurements, it is shown that the improvement in the functioning of the OSCs cannot be ascribed to morphology-related processes in the donor–acceptor intermixing scale. Moreover, the J – V characteristics showed an improvement in the FF in the diode region, i.e., an improvement related to a decrease in recombination current. Provided that the decrease in recombination rate is believed to arise through a longer effective

lifetime of the photogenerated excitons (τ_{eff}), this feature is expected to appear as higher rates of phosphorescence and/or delayed fluorescence (DF) compared with prompt fluorescence (PF) signal. Therefore, samples were electronically characterized with the aid of photoluminescence (PL) measurements. The samples with different concentrations of Fe_3O_4 NPs were excited with monochromatic light with a wavelength of $\lambda = 485$ nm. Two main response signals were identified: the first corresponds to PF. The other is identified as DF, since it exhibits the same profile as the PF.^[26] This DF signal is measured at four different delay times (10, 20, 30, and 40 μs after the excitation). The corresponding signal profiles as a function of the wavelength are shown in Figure S3 (Supporting Information). **Figure 5a** depicts the integrated intensity for the two profiles (PF as hollow squares and DF as solid squares) as a function of Fe_3O_4 NP concentration. Both signals decrease in intensity in the region of the solar cell improvement, indicating generally a higher level of exciton quenching, i.e., a decreased recombination rate, regardless of the energy band at which the exciton was before the recombination. In order to address the latter question, Figure 5b displays the DF-to-PF ratio. This ratio shows the portion of excitons that migrated from the singlet to the triplet manifold (intersystem crossing) and back to the singlet state via triplet-triplet annihilation (TTA). It is increased for low concentrations of Fe_3O_4 NPs with respect to the value of the reference sample (slightly larger as 84%). Beyond a Fe_3O_4 NP concentration of 1.5 wt%, DF-to-PF ratios are back to the reference value or even lower.

DF measurements were performed with four delay times, as mentioned above, with a time resolution of 10 μs . Despite this very limited time resolution, the decay in intensity is modeled as an exponential function, yielding a characteristic decay time constant proportional to the exciton effective lifetime τ_{eff} (see Figure 5c). The error associated with each value is the error extracted from the fitting (see Supporting Information). The exciton effective lifetime τ_{eff} increases by more than 34% from the reference value of 4.9–6.6 μs for the most efficient solar cell (0.6 wt% NPs). It is important to consider that the effective exciton lifetime determined from the decay rate of a DF measurement series depends on factors inherent to the PL method itself, as it is, e.g., the measurement protocol employed (described in the Experimental Section), or to other recombination mechanisms whose decay rate does not correlate with the exciton lifetime, as it is the nongeminate recombination. As a result, we obtain an effective lifetime that integrates all these factors together. Thereby, we need to avoid to great extent to draw inferences on their absolute values, but it allows us for comparison amongst different effective lifetimes, provided that the measurement parameters are kept constant and that the inner domain morphology can be assumed as statistically unchanged. The latter hypothesis is moreover confirmed by GISAXS measurements.

The obtained results are in excellent agreement with the ones obtained from the J - V characteristics. The increased τ_{eff} of the photogenerated excitons, arising from a higher rate of DF due to the enhanced spin-orbit coupling, is appointed as the effect responsible for the reduced recombination. It has been already reported that shorter τ_{eff} correspond to higher recombination rates, an effect that competes with the extraction of charge carriers.^[48] Moreover, this effect cannot be related to any morphology changes.

Figure 5. a) Integrated prompt (hollow squares) and delayed (solid squares) fluorescence signals, b) ratio of delayed fluorescence (DF) to prompt fluorescence (PF), and c) effective exciton lifetime τ_{eff} plotted versus the concentration of Fe_3O_4 NPs. Squares indicate the data points whereas the dashed lines are guide to the eye.

Figure 6. 2D GIWAXS data of the P3HT:PCBM samples doped with a) 0 wt%, b) 0.1 wt%, c) 0.6 wt%, d) 0.8 wt%, e) 1.05 wt%, f) 2.0 wt%, g) 3.0 wt% and h) 4.0 wt% of Fe_3O_4 NPs. Images are corrected for q_{xy} versus q_z representation. Tube cuts in h) indicate the radially integrated areas of the (100) and (010) directions selected for the crystalline analysis.

After finding a satisfactory explanation for the improvement in OSC functioning in the region of light Fe_3O_4 NP doping (below 1.0 wt%), it raises the question whether an explanation for the worsened functioning of the solar cells for NP concentrations higher as 1.0 wt% can be found.

The PL characterization (Figure 5) shows a decrease in DF-to-PF ratio for samples doped with Fe_3O_4 NPs at concentrations higher as 1.0 wt%. This decrease is attributed to the population dependence of the TTA decay mechanism. TTA is the primary decay mechanism affecting the triplet excitons in organic devices/films. This decay mechanism takes place when two triplet excitons meet each other, annihilate, and result in one exciton in a triplet excited state in 75% of the events (which will in short time scales decay nonradiatively to a ground triplet), whereas the second one directly falls nonradiatively into the singlet ground state, thereby yielding a net loss of one triplet exciton.^[49,50] The efficiency of this recombination mechanism scales quadratic with the population of triplet excitons.^[50] Provided that higher Fe_3O_4 NP concentrations induce a higher presence of triplet excitons, it implies that the TTA can occur fast enough, and that it shortens “de facto” the overall exciton effective lifetime τ_{eff} by reducing the triplet population. If a certain percentage of triplet excitons start recombining in short time scales, they would contribute to the PF signal instead of to the DF one, thereby decreasing the DF-to-PF ratio, as is displayed in Figure 5b for Fe_3O_4 NPs doping using concentrations of 1.5 wt% or higher. Moreover, TTA presents a certain percentage (25% of TTA events) of decay in an excited singlet plus a ground one ($T_1 + T_1 = S_1 + S_0$). This percentage increases with the increasing amount of triplet-triplet collisions (TTC), i.e., with the increasing

population of triplet excitons. Therefore, this fact can also be responsible for the decay in DF-to-PF signal for high doping levels, since the increased population of triplet excitons and, therefore, of TTC makes this decay pathway more efficient.^[50,51]

Regarding the performance of the OSCs (depicted in Figures 1–3), the worsened performance for those with NP concentrations higher as 1.0 wt% is ascribed to enhanced leakage currents in the solar device, due to conductive pathways created by the increased amount of Fe_3O_4 NPs. This explanation is in excellent agreement with the values of shunt resistance obtained from the J - V characteristics (Figure 3), in which it can be seen how R_{SH} starts decreasing from 0.8 wt% NPs. Values of R_{SH} for doping levels as higher as 1.0 wt% are not displayed, since they basically correspond to short-circuited solar cells, yielding in the analysis even negative values of R_{SH} for NP concentrations of 2.0 wt% or beyond.

2.4. Crystalline Characterization (GIWAXS)

Grazing-incidence wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS) measurements were performed on the P3HT:PCBM films with different Fe_3O_4 NP concentrations in order to track the evolution of their crystalline regions. Incorporation of Fe_3O_4 NPs in the organic film can also influence the crystallinity of the active layers of the OSCs, which in turn affects the electrical conductivity of the final device. **Figure 6** displays the 2D GIWAXS data of the P3HT:PCBM with different amounts of Fe_3O_4 NPs.

From the 2D GIWAXS data, it can be seen how the Bragg peak corresponding to the π - π stacking (outer ring highlighted

in red in Figure 6h), referred to as the 010 orientation, broadens with increasing Fe_3O_4 NP concentration. For 0.0 wt% NP concentration, it shows a preferential orientation perpendicular to the substrate (interference maximum along $q_{xy} = 0 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ direction). The Bragg peak broadening originates from the transformation of a prominent face-on orientation into more isotropically oriented crystals. The same behavior can be observed for the (100) Bragg peak, which gives the backbone spacing (inner ring in Figure 6h). The interference maximum along the q_z direction broadens until it becomes a ring-like feature. Thus, a prominent edge-on orientation at 0.0 wt% Fe_3O_4 NPs turns into more randomly oriented crystallites with increasing NP concentration. Moreover, the amount of edge-on-oriented crystals increases with increasing NP concentration, as can be seen from the higher order Bragg peaks. Up to this point, it is noteworthy to mention that an increase in edge-on-oriented crystals to detriment of the face-on orientation is eventually harmful for the device vertical conductivity, since the mobility of charge carriers in a P3HT crystal along the π - π stacked planes is higher than that along the P3HT side chains, where the conductivity is negligible due to the lack of conjugated bonds.^[52,53] To gain a more quantitative insight in the face-on to edge-on evolution, tube cuts are performed along the (100) Bragg peak. By selecting different angular ranges corresponding to edge-on and face-on orientations within these tube cuts, and integrating the total intensity under the curve for the selected ranges, we are able to determine the face-on to edge-on ratio for each sample (presented in Figure S4, Supporting Information). More detailed information about the analysis related to the GIWAXS measurements is given in the Supporting Information. **Figure 7** displays the face-on to edge-on evolution for the different P3HT:PCBM samples as a function of the Fe_3O_4 NP concentration. The ratio remains rather constant up to 1.0 wt%. At higher NP concentrations, the ratio decays down to less than one third of its initial value for NP concentrations of 4.0 wt%.

In addition to a lowered face-on to edge-on ratio, determined from the analysis of the tube cuts performed on the (100) Bragg peak, the edge-on orientation becomes less defined. Its corresponding scattering feature broadens as the NP concentration

Figure 7. Face-on to edge-on ratio calculated from the (100) Bragg peak and plotted versus the Fe_3O_4 concentration. Dashed line is a guide to the eye.

increases, indicating a worsened orientation with the backbone spacing perpendicular to the substrate. This fact is observed directly from the 2D GIWAXS data (Figure 6a–h). For a quantitative analysis, cuts from the 2D GIWAXS data at the (100) Bragg peak position are performed along $q_{xy} = 0 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ and fitted with Gaussian functions. The resulting fits are displayed in **Figure 8a**. On the one hand, it can be seen how the intensity

Figure 8. a) Gaussian fits to the (100) Bragg peaks of the Fe_3O_4 doped P3HT:PCBM films. Data are plotted in intensity versus angle with respect to the substrate surface. b) FWHM of the fits to the (100) peaks in degrees versus the wt% of Fe_3O_4 NPs. c) Inverse of the FWHM of the fits to the (100) peaks and short-circuit current J_{sc} of the corresponding solar cells plotted versus the concentration of Fe_3O_4 NPs. Solid and hollow squares are data points and dashed lines are guide to the eye.

of the edge-on phase increases with the Fe_3O_4 NP concentration, as already discussed above. On the other hand, one notices how the edge-on orientation worsens with increasing presence of NPs. The full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the corresponding fittings increases, eventually also leading to worsened vertical conductivity. Figure 8b displays the FWHM of the edge-on-oriented (100) crystals as a function of the concentration of Fe_3O_4 NPs. It remains reasonably constant up to NP concentrations of 1.0 wt%. At higher NP concentrations, it increases up to more than double of the amount of the reference sample. Interestingly, we are able to relate the evolution of the edge-on crystal orientation to the behavior of the short-circuit current (J_{SC}) of the solar cells. The inverse of the edge-on FWHM fit is plotted along with the J_{SC} in Figure 8c.

The plot of both parameters shows an excellent agreement, especially in the range of light doping. It has been previously shown how the morphology and the arrangement of donor and acceptor materials play a capital role in the behavior of J_{SC} .^[54] Provided that the changes in morphology in the present case due to inclusion of Fe_3O_4 NPs are negligible, we conclude that the evolution of the crystalline regions in the organic film, leading to a worsened orientation of the aggregates, is related to that of the J_{SC} of the device in the early stages of doping, where the device J_{SC} shows a mild decrease as well as the inverse of the (100) edge-on FWHM does. However, for the range of heavy doping, the conductive pathways created by the Fe_3O_4 NPs are expected to also have a strong influence on the J_{SC} of the device.

3. Conclusion

In the present study, we report on BHJ P3HT:PCBM solar cells with enhanced PCE through the presence of Fe_3O_4 NPs. The improvement in performance arises at low NP concentrations (below 1.0 wt%) through an improved FF, meaning a lowered recombination current. This behavior was expected, since the presence of heavy atoms provides the system with an increased spin-orbit coupling, which in turn increases the efficiency of the exciton intersystem crossing process in the device. This translates into a longer effective exciton lifetime τ_{eff} and thereby a lowered recombination current.

The improvement appears in the J - V characteristics of the OSCs as an improvement in the FF in the diode region, associated with a lowered device ideality factor and therefore not influenced by changes in series (R_{S}) or shunt resistances (R_{SH}). These values on the other hand stay reasonably constant in the whole range of PCE improvement, indicating that the PCE improvement cannot be ascribed to different performance of cell contacts or different amounts of leakage currents.

The electronic characterization of the active layers showed an improved DF-to-PF ratio, supporting the finding of a longer τ_{eff} due to a higher rate of spin-orbit coupling extracted from the J - V analysis. Moreover, the DF decay time constant was extracted from DF measurements performed at different delay times, showing an increase in τ_{eff} of over 34%. Besides the strong indications that relate the improvement in OSC func-

tioning to a longer exciton τ_{eff} , the enhancement is not ascribed

to major changes in the morphology or the crystalline arrangement, according to the GISAXS and GIWAXS results.

For the range of high Fe_3O_4 NP concentrations, the OSCs showed short-circuited behavior. This is attributed to an enhanced leakage current due to conductive pathways created by the increased presence of metal oxide NPs as indicated by the observed shunt resistance (R_{SH}) behavior obtained from the analysis of the J - V characteristics. In addition, a very plausible link for the worsened OSC performance is found between the evolution of P3HT crystalline regions and the J_{SC} of the corresponding solar devices. As a consequence, the addition of heavy NPs to the active layer is an interesting option to further enhance the PCEs of OSCs.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: The following materials and/or chemicals were used without further purification: P3HT (regioregular, $M_w = 53\text{k}$, regioregularity 92%, PDI = 2.3, Rieke Metals, Inc.), PC₆₀BM ([6,6]-phenyl-C₆₀-butyric acid methyl ester, purity $\geq 99.5\%$, Nano-C, Inc.), Fe_3O_4 NPs (iron (II,III) oxide, 5 mg mL⁻¹ solution in toluene, <1.0% OA stabilizing ligands, Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC) prepared via high-temperature decomposition of iron precursors in the presence of hot organic surfactants and capped with OA as surfactant to provide compatibility with organic solvents,^[55,56] PEDOT:PSS (poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):polystyrene sulfonate, M122 PEDOT:PSS PH 1000, Ossila Ltd.), toluene (C₇H₈, purity $\geq 99.9\%$, Carl Roth GmbH).

Sample Preparation: Thin films used for electrical, morphological, and crystalline characterization were deposited on top of pre-cleaned silicon (Si) substrates, which were coated with a PEDOT:PSS layer to mimic the interface relevant for the solar cells. The cleaning procedure was an acid cleaning at 80 °C for 15 min. The cleaning bath was a mixture of distilled water (H₂O), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂ 30%), and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄ 96%), mixed at a ratio of 16.1:25:58.9. After the bath, the substrates were thoroughly rinsed with distilled water (H₂O) and dried with oil-free nitrogen (N₂). The PEDOT:PSS layer was deposited on the cleaned Si substrates via spin coating (3500 rpm, $a = 9$, $t = 60$ s) after the PEDOT:PSS solution had been ultrasonicated for 15 min and filtered with a polytetrafluoroethylene filter with a pore size of 0.45 μm . Afterwards, the PEDOT:PSS layer was annealed in air at 140 °C for 10 min. On top of the PEDOT:PSS layer, the active layer consisting of P3HT:PC₆₀BM:Fe₃O₄ NPs was deposited with spin coating as well (2000 rpm, $a = 9$, $t = 30$ s). The P3HT:PC₆₀BM:Fe₃O₄ solution was prepared at a concentration of 16 mg mL⁻¹ and based on toluene. The P3HT:PCBM solution was prepared in the first place. Both P3HT and PCBM solution are first stirred separately for 70–90 min. Afterwards, both solutions are mixed in a 1:1 ratio and they are further stirred together for another 30–50 min. Meanwhile, the Fe₃O₄ NP solution is ultrasonicated for 15 min at room temperature to avoid aggregation. A certain amount of solution is then added to the P3HT:PCBM mixture until the desired Fe₃O₄ concentration is reached. Prior to the spin coating step, the final solution is further ultrasonicated (for 30–60 s) and stirred shortly. The total stirring time amounts to approximately 2 h and has been always done at 55 °C in sand bath. After deposition, an annealing step of 10 min under N₂ atmosphere is applied.

For solar cell preparation, PEDOT:PSS and P3HT:PC₆₀BM:Fe₃O₄ layers were deposited following the same routine used for fabrication of thin films. The differences between the preparation of thin films and that of solar cells addressed the different substrates used and the final back electrode deposition. The substrates used to manufacture the solar cells consisted of indium tin oxide-coated glasses (50 Ω , Solems S. A.), which were cleaned by ultrasonication in Alconox, ethanol, acetone, and 2-propanol each for 15 min, dried with oil-free N₂ and afterwards

subjected to a O₂-plasma cleaning process (Plasma-System-Nano, Diener electronic GmbH) for 10 min. In solar cell production, after

deposition of the PEDOT:PSS and P3HT:PC₆₀BM:Fe₃O₄ layers and their corresponding annealing steps, aluminum (Al) back electrodes were

thermally deposited under high vacuum conditions, followed by a final annealing step at 140 °C in N₂ atmosphere.

Measurements: *J*-*V* characteristics of the produced OSCs were collected in air atmosphere with a solar simulator Solar Constant1200 (K.H. Steuernagel Lichttechnik GmbH) equipped with a rare earth halogen lamp. OSCs were measured both in dark and in AM 1.5 conditions, the latter with an emission power density of 1000 W m⁻². The light intensity was corrected with a calibrated silicon reference photodiode (WPVS, CalLab-Fraunhofer ISE). For each concentration of Fe₃O₄ NPs, four individual solar cells were prepared simultaneously. In total, around 70 solar cells were prepared for this study. All the mean values and associated error bars depicted in the following are calculated from the deviation of parameters for the corresponding set of solar cells.

PL measurements were performed with an LS55 spectrometer (PerkinElmer) with a Xenon discharge lamp for illumination. DF measurements were performed with time delays of 10, 20, 30, and 40 μs after the excitation, gate time of 10 μs, flash count = 1, and cycle = 20.

GISAXS and GIWAXS measurements were performed in the P03 beamline, at the PETRAIII storage ring at DESY, Hamburg.^[44,57] X-ray beam energy of 13 keV was used. For the GISAXS setup, the incident angle was set to 0.35° and the sample-to-detector distance (SDD) was 2.55 m. For the GIWAXS measurements, the incident angle was set to 0.15° and the SDD was 153 mm. The detectors used for recording the scattering signal for GISAXS and GIWAXS experiments were a Pilatus 1M and a Pilatus 300k, respectively (Dectris, Switzerland). Both detectors had a pixel size of 172 × 172 μm². In total, two complete batches of samples were fabricated and characterized with GISAXS/GIWAXS.

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